

An IOT Enabled Intelligent Automobile Driving Assistant System (IADAS)

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Abstract:

Technology is evolving in the world day by day. This development involves the solution of all human problems. In addition, modern technological discoveries have paved the way for multifunctional devices. It also made human life convenient, safe and easy. However, many situations miserably damage people's lives. One of these situations is traffic accidents; The most common cause of this problem is driver fatigue due to drowsiness. The use of IoT technology with the DL algorithm reduces traffic accidents. These IoT devices make it possible to ensure driver and vehicle safety. Traffic accidents are a serious problem because they cause numerous bodily injuries, sometimes resulting in death. One of the causes of accidents is the driver's drowsiness while driving. Using Internet-of-Things technology, we create an Intelligent Automobile Driving Assistant System (IADAS). This system helps reduce traffic accidents and protects the driver and vehicle. is collision avoidance using machine learning technologies and the Internet of Things. It also detects drowsiness with various sensors and provides vehicle stability control with the Edge Line Crossing sensor and warning system that generates audible warnings and reduces vehicle ground speed (servo/DC motors can be used for prototypes). We use the DL algorithm to detect the drowsy state by identifying the driver's eyes and identity. Even if the driver is drowsy, this system can provide a remote notification system. This system helps track the location of the drivers and vehicles using the GPS location navigator system and send the SMS to the appropriate authority.